

Inflection Point Principle Combined with Digital Image Correlation and Machine Learning for Crack Length Measurement in Fatigue Tests

Borek Ščerba^a, Tomáš Adamec^a, Pavel Pokorný^b, Tomáš Návrat^a, Michal Vajdák^c, Luboš Náhlík^b

^a Institute of Solid Mechanics, Mechatronics and Biomechanics, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Brno University of Technology, Technická 2896/2, 616 69 Brno, Czech Republic

* Borek.Scerba@vutbr.cz

* Tomas.Adamec@vutbr.cz

* navrat@fme.vutbr.cz (corresponding author)

^b Institute of Physics of Materials, Czech Academy of Sciences, Žižkova, 616 00 Brno, Czech Republic

* pokorny@ipm.cz

* nahlik@ipm.cz

^c X-Sight s.r.o., Staňkova 557/18a, 602 00, Brno, Czech Republic

* michal.vajdak@xsight.eu

Abstract

The visual inspection method is a widely used non-contact technique for measuring fatigue crack propagation. However, it is inefficient, requiring frequent operator intervention and suffering from low accuracy and measurement ambiguity. While current methods based on digital image correlation offer potential solutions, they present their own challenges: full-field approaches are computationally demanding, while thresholding techniques depend on factors like material properties and load levels, making them difficult to apply consistently. This study proposes and validates a new non-contact, physically-based method for real-time crack length evaluation. It eliminates the need for threshold values and allows continuous measurement during testing due to its line-based nature. It is designed to facilitate easier, more accurate, versatile, and fully automated fatigue testing. The method combines the inflection point principle with modern techniques such as digital image correlation and machine learning. The visual inspection method serves as a baseline for validation. An innovative experimental setup allows both methods to be applied simultaneously on the same side of the sample for direct comparison. The proposed method shows good agreement with the baseline visual inspection results. Its feasibility for real-time use during testing was successfully demonstrated. A comparison with the thresholding approach highlights the superior accuracy and versatility of the proposed method. The presented method expands the capabilities of non-contact measurements using digital image correlation and a line-based evaluation approach in the field of metals fatigue testing. Its accuracy, versatility, and potential for full automation also open the door for future applications in the testing of other materials.

Keywords Digital Image Correlation, Crack Length Measurement, Inflection Point Method, Gaussian Process Regression, Machine Learning

1. Introduction

Violation of body integrity through sudden fracture is an undesirable phenomenon in all structures, a concern that gained prominence during the industrial revolution with the increased use of iron and steel. It was during this period that the first pioneering works on the subject emerged [1–6]. However, the foundation for modern fracture mechanics was laid by Griffith in his contributions [7,8]. Since then, numerous quantitative approaches have been proposed to assess the impact of cracks, as exemplified by Irwin [9,10], Orowan [11], Wells [12], Rice [13] or Paris [14], wherein the crack length, typically denoted as a , is considered the essential parameter. Consequently, mastering its determination in related experiments becomes imperative.

Numerous conventional crack length measurement methods have been developed, continually refined, and are still in use for both monotonic and cyclic tests. Examples include the compliance method [15,16], the electric potential drop technique [17], the foil strain gauge approach [18,19], the crack opening displacement (COD) technique [20,21], and the widely used visual inspection method (VIM) [22,23].

When determining the length of a fatigue crack in a cyclic test via VIM, a traveling microscope or another optical magnifying device is commonly employed. The apparatus allows technicians to locate the crack tip and measure its position to ascertain the crack length. Typically, this measurement is conducted when the test is paused, requiring intervention from the operator. This conventional non-contact approach prompts the question: Is it feasible to perform non-contact measurement of the crack length without interrupting the test, as recommended by relevant standards [24]? Doing so could alleviate operator burden, streamline the measurement process, and pave the way for automation. The solution to this query may lie in the application of the digital image correlation (DIC).

1.1 Digital image correlation

Digital image correlation is an optically-based technique used to measure the evolving full-field 2D or 3D coordinates on the surface of a test piece throughout a mechanical test [25]. Introduced in 1980s [26], DIC algorithms have undergone remarkable progress, establishing themselves as one of the most powerful non-destructive and non-contact surface deformation measurement techniques in a wide range of experimental mechanics applications [27]. Thanks to the implementation of subpixel interpolation for increased accuracy [28], DIC can achieve quality measurements even with relatively low-resolution cameras [29]. The availability of many open-source codes (such as AL-DIC in Matlab, Ncorr in Matlab, PReDIC in Python, etc.) and commercial software (like VIC from Correlated Solutions, GOM from Zeiss Group, Alpha from X-Sight, etc.) has made DIC a competitive and cost-effective solution.

DIC provides a distinctive benefit by enabling a comprehensive understanding of material behavior through the measurement of displacements or strains across the entire field of view. This full-field measurement capability allows for a more holistic approach offering valuable insights, which traditional methods may not provide. The non-contact nature of DIC, minimal requirements for sample preparation, a relatively simple measuring system setup, low demands on the experimental environment and testing sample, a high degree of automation in measurement and data processing, and compatibility with various magnifying instruments or other devices [30] collectively enhance its appeal in experimental mechanics. This array of advantages positions DIC as a versatile and powerful tool, facilitating a more thorough and nuanced analysis of mechanical behavior in fracture mechanics studies.

1.2 DIC in crack length measurement

Different approaches for determining crack length or the associated position of the crack tip using DIC have been presented by various authors in the literature, primarily relying on full-field measurements. Several studies concentrate on fitting mathematical terms - functions of distance and angular position in a coordinate system with the origin at the crack tip and one axis coinciding with the direction of crack propagation - to the deformation field [31–34], such as the Williams series. In this approach, the crack length becomes one of the resultant parameters of optimization. However, it is computationally demanding, requiring 3 to 5 minutes for the calculation of a single image [33].

Réthoré et al. [35] enhance the DIC algorithm by integrating shape functions from X-FEM¹, allowing for a more accurate description of discontinuities in the displacement field caused by the presence of the crack, aiding in crack tip localization. Roux et al. [36] adopt a similar approach for studying 3D cracks, utilizing digital volume correlation (DVC) in images obtained through magnetic resonance. Fangerholt et al. [37] also employ a FEM-based DIC approach but implement the node splitting technique, achieving better results in cases with significant plastic deformation followed by ductile fracture. Durif et al. [38] utilize FEM-based 2D DIC to determine discontinuities, with the crack length determined from the COD profile along it.

Other authors frequently determine crack length by analyzing discontinuities in the strain field by employing various edge detection algorithms [39–41], such as the Sobel-Feldman operator², or their custom approach exploiting the large gradient in the strain field along the crack path [42]. Carroll et al. [43] use accumulated plastic strain values determined by 2D DIC ex situ, along with visual investigation under an optical

¹ allows to model the crack growth without remeshing by incorporating discontinuous fields and the near tip asymptotic fields [80]

² is an isotropic 3x3 gradient operator [81]

microscope, to determine the crack tip. Some authors [44–46] identify the crack tip location as the point along the crack path where the COD reaches zero. Many authors [47–51] determine the crack tip or crack length using a technique in this work referred to as the deformation threshold method (DTM). In this method, the crack tip is identified as the location along the crack path where the strain or displacement (in the direction from the ligament to the notch) exceeds a certain threshold value.

Some studies utilize more sophisticated techniques like 3D DIC [52] or DVC [36] which involve considerable hardware and possibly software investments. Moreover, the latter method is fairly impractical for real-time measurements. Nevertheless, for fatigue tests primarily involving planar surfaces and minimal out-of-plane deformation, 2D measurements, as discussed in the majority of the cited literature, suffice.

When employing 2D full-field measurements, it becomes crucial to choose an appropriate density for the DIC mesh on which displacements or strains are calculated, necessitating a trade-off between accuracy and computational complexity, which can be substantial. On the other hand, the undeniable advantage of this approach lies in its ability to capture crack propagation in any direction, along with the possibility to extract additional parameters such as crack tip opening displacement (CTOD) [42], stress intensity factor (SIF) [33], or to explore related phenomena, for instance, crack closure [53] or the plastic zone [54]. In summary, the use of 2D DIC full-field measurements proves to be a universal and versatile approach for fatigue testing analysis, and undoubtedly, it holds significance in other areas of fracture mechanics as well.

The standard for testing fatigue crack growth rates specifies that the crack must grow in a straight line, and if the crack deviates too far from this line, the test is considered invalid [24]. Consequently, it is possible to streamline the 2D full-field measurement into the line-based approach, which will be here referred to as a 1D approach or 1D DIC. This technique focuses solely on extracting deformations along the expected crack path. By narrowing the scope of measurement, computational time is greatly reduced, and real-time usability is significantly enhanced. This improvement is critical for automating cyclic tests using DIC, which is essential for adaptive testing strategies. These strategies enable the optimization of load conditions based on the material's response, further increasing the efficiency of the testing process.

The 1D approach has already been utilized in some of the cited papers [44–46] and is available in certain DIC software developed by companies like Imetrum [55] and X-Sight [56]. However, only the phenomenological DTM has been employed to determine the crack length so far. The main challenge with this method lies in correctly determining the threshold value, which can vary based on factors such as material properties, sample size, or the level of applied load. This variability may necessitate creating a threshold value

database tailored to specific use cases. This limitation, which the authors consider substantial, was the driving force behind proposing a new method that takes into account the nature of the measured phenomena.

1.3 Inflection point principle

The phenomena in question can be elucidated by the works of Barenblatt [57] and Dugdale [58], who were among the first authors to introduce the concept of molecular cohesive forces ahead of the crack tip. In this scenario, when the distance between opposing crack faces is small, they attract each other powerfully. However, as the distance between crack faces increases, this attraction intensity diminishes, resulting in the smooth unification of crack faces and the formation of a cusp-like shape. This stands in contrast to the ‘unnaturally rounded’ [57] shape considered in previous approaches. The region where cohesive forces dominate is often referred to as the fracture process zone (FPZ³), while the region behind the crack tip is considered stress-free. When expressing the inherent crack shape, such as through COD, the transition between these two regions is reflected in the presence of an inflection point (IP), as illustrated in Fig. 1. According to sources that consider cohesive forces, such as [59], the crack tip is located at the junction of these two regions and is used to determine the crack length.

Fig. 1 The shape of the opened crack, with coordinates x representing the distance from the notch tip and y representing the displacement, including the inflection point. The shape is symmetrical with respect to the x -axis, and only one half is displayed. The radial coordinate system with coordinates (r, θ) used for deformation calculations is shown on the right, while the principle of the deformation threshold method is illustrated on the left, where y_{th} represents the threshold value and DTM deformation threshold method. IP means inflection point.

³ is a region with disordered internal structure and nonlinear material behavior that evolves at the tip of a propagating crack [82], where microcracking occurs and the macrocrack is formed [83]. It is also referred to as the process zone.

Additionally, numerous studies on the FPZ have employed nonlocal elasticity⁴, specifically gradient elasticity theory [60], which supports the cusp-like shape of the crack and the presence of the IP. For example, Sciarra and Vidoli [61] demonstrated that for isotropic materials, strain gradient elasticity can provide the same CODs as those obtained assuming cohesive forces. Skalka et al. [62] compared a discrete FE model of a ceramic foam-like structure with a homogenized model incorporating strain gradient elasticity theory to calculate the COD profile, showing a good match. They asserted that the IP marks the transition from the cusp-like closure zone with cohesive-like behavior, scaling as $(r^{\frac{3}{2}}, \theta = \pi \text{ rad})$, to the far-field COD shape $(r^{\frac{1}{2}}, \theta = \pi \text{ rad})$, obtained by the classical elasticity solution. Here, r and θ are coordinates in the radial coordinate system with the origin at the crack tip, see e.g. [63]. The coordinate system is also illustrated in Fig. 1. Kotoul et al. [64] presented a comparison of results from the atomistic approach using ab-initio density functional theory calculations and strain gradient elasticity theory, demonstrating good agreement. In their work, the CTOD is evaluated at the IP, suggesting its association with the crack tip.

As for applying this principle to practical fatigue crack length determination using DIC, only one study [51], focusing on fatigue testing of polymers, has addressed this area. The study suggests a correlation between the crack tip location and the position of the IP in the DIC measured data. However, the reliability of this suggestion might be questionable due to the methodology employed. It is based on a comparison of the crack length measured by VIM using a traveling microscope positioned on the opposite side of the compact tension (CT) sample to the DIC measurement. The paper notes that crack length measurements on one side may not match those on the other, recommending comparisons on the same side of the sample. Furthermore, no details are provided regarding the settings of the DIC algorithm or the approach used to extract the IP.

1.4 Scope of the study

In addressing the research gaps associated with the currently prevalent visual inspection method for assessing fatigue crack length, and the limitations of the 1D DIC crack length estimation based on the deformation threshold method, this study introduces a physically-based approach for 1D DIC crack length measurement of metals: the inflection point method (IPM). The IPM innovatively combines the inflection point principle with DIC and machine learning. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this combination represents an unprecedented approach in real-time fatigue crack length determination for metallic materials.

⁴ assumes that the nonlocal stress at a reference point depends not only on the strain in that location, but also on strains of all other location within certain domain [84].

In the scope of this study, the inflection point principle is validated as an integral part of the proposed method, along with testing its reliability, versatility, and accuracy. The validation of the method and its underlying principle is performed using an unprecedented approach designed specifically for this study, which accounts for potential discrepancies in crack length observed on opposite faces of the sample. The preliminary results of the inflection point principle validation were presented in [65]. Moreover, a comprehensive comparison between the widely used DTM and the newly proposed IPM is presented, highlighting their benefits and drawbacks. Additionally, user recommendations are formulated to ease the practical application of this method. The study also provides a basis for further development, including the potential application of the IPM to fatigue tests of other materials.

2. Experimental procedure

The experiment was designed to validate the proposed IPM and its underlying principle. To ensure robust validation, the experiment incorporated various metal materials, specimen thicknesses, and load levels. The visual inspection method was selected as the baseline for validation.

2.1 Sample materials, dimensions and preparation

Standard CT samples as defined by ASTM E647 [24] were used. The materials were chosen to effectively cover the spectrum of commonly inspected metallic materials at the testing facility of the Institute of Physics of Materials of the Czech Academy of Sciences: low alloy steel 38MnVS6, stainless steel 1.4306, and aluminum alloy EN AW-7075. Three samples of varying thicknesses (B) were available for stainless steel, allowing the versatility of the proposed method to be tested with respect to this variable. For each of the other materials, two samples of the same thickness were prepared. All samples shared the same width (W), length of the machined notch (a_n), and notch type. Table 1 provides a comprehensive overview of the samples used in the experiment, detailing the specific dimensions and materials for each sample.

Table 1 Overview of standard^a CT samples for experiment

Material	Pieces	W^b [mm]	B^c [mm]	a_n^d [mm]	Notch type
38MnVS6	2	50	0.2 W	0.25 W	Chevron
1.4306	1	50	0.1 W	0.25 W	Chevron
1.4306	1	50	0.2 W	0.25 W	Chevron
1.4306	1	50	0.3 W	0.25 W	Chevron
EN AW-7075	2	50	0.2 W	0.25 W	Chevron

^a according to ASTM E647 [24]

^b width

^c thickness

^d length of machined notch

To improve the visibility of the crack tip for the application of VIM, the surface of the sample was grounded and polished using diamond paste with abrasive particles as small as $0.25\ \mu\text{m}$, resulting in a mirror-like finish. The grinding and polishing movements were applied perpendicular to the anticipated crack path to prevent confusion between surface treatment marks and the crack itself. A band of the polished surface approximately 0.8 to 1.2 mm wide was preserved along the expected crack growth path, while the remaining area was covered with matte white paint and later sprayed with black paint. This process created a random, anisotropic, and highly contrasting speckle pattern required for DIC. The resulting surface condition on the CT sample is illustrated in Fig. 2, along with a detailed view of the polished band. This approach allowed for the use of both VIM and DIC on the same side of the sample, effectively excluding the influence of nonuniform crack growth over the sample thickness from the methods comparison.

Fig. 2 CT sample with applied DIC speckle pattern (left) and the detail of the polished band and the speckles (right)

2.2 Testing machine and optical system specifications

The tests were performed using the Amsler 20 HFP 5100 resonant pulsator machine. Image acquisition was conducted by a FLIR 8.9-megapixel global shutter camera equipped with a TC3MHR016-C telecentric lens at 0.85 magnification. This setup provided the viewing area of approximately 16.6 mm x 8.8 mm. The global shutter was essential due to the high movement speeds during the experiment, as a rolling shutter camera would cause motion-induced image distortion. The telecentric lens was chosen to minimize perspective errors inherent in entocentric lenses commonly used in 2D DIC applications. Additionally, telecentric lenses exhibit minimal image distortion [66], eliminating the need for distortion compensation.

To address the low lens speed and short exposure time (0.5 ms), two 50 W LED lights were strategically positioned close to the sample to ensure adequate illumination. The camera was securely mounted on a slider to

enable precise focus adjustment of the optical system, as telecentric lenses have a fixed focal length and shallow depth of focus. The experimental setup, including the arrangement of the optical system, is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Detail of the experimental setup in front of the testing machine

2.3 Testing process

Each test commenced with the calibration of the DIC using an object of known dimensions, which served for determination of the pixel-to-millimeter conversion ratio. Additionally, prior to the initiation of cycling, an image of the undeformed sample was captured to act as a reference for DIC deformation calculations.

Throughout the experiment, the test was periodically halted (also referred to as readout) at various crack lengths to gather high-quality images for the VIM, which also formed the static dataset for the IPM and DTM. The stopping intervals were determined based on previous increments in crack length, aiming for the most uniform distribution of crack lengths. To further enhance the visibility of the crack tip, an overload of approximately 33% (compared to the maximum cyclic load F_{max}) was applied during the readout. Since the experiment's objective was to compare measured crack lengths between methods rather than conduct a valid investigation of crack growth rates, this overload had no adverse effects on the results. The testing procedure, including the periodic halting and application of overload, is schematically depicted in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Scheme of the testing procedure, including periodic halting (readout) between the cyclic phases and application of overload during the readout

The test frequency was determined by the dynamic characteristics of the machine-sample system and couldn't be manually adjusted. Typically, for this experiment, the cycle frequency started around 90 Hz and gradually decreased to approximately 60 Hz as the presence of the growing crack reduced the sample's stiffness.

2.4 Load levels

The cycle parameters were chosen to achieve an R ratio⁵ of 0.1, representing the pulsating tension cycle commonly used for such tests at the testing facility. Higher forces were applied for crack initiation up to approximately 1 mm in length. Subsequently, the load levels corresponding to F_{max} were set⁶, as detailed in the Table 2. For the materials with two identical CT samples, F_{max} slightly differed to introduce some additional variations into the validation.

Table 2 Overview of applied loads for cycling after crack initiation

<i>Material</i>	<i>Piece No.</i>	F_{max}^a [kN]
38MnVS6	1	6.5
38MnVS6	2	5.5
1.4306	1	10.8
1.4306	2	7.2
1.4306	3	3.7
EN AW-7075	1	3.6
EN AW-7075	2	2.7

^a Maximum force in the R = 0.1 loading cycle

In the case of the EN AW-7075 No. 1 sample, the applied load was excessively high, causing the crack to deviate from the plane of symmetry early in the test (approximately 2 mm from the notch), and the crack tip became hidden under the thin layer of paint. Therefore, VIM was not applicable, and the dataset obtained from this sample is excluded from further analysis due to the missing validation data. The test of the EN AW-7075 No. 2 sample was consequently conducted with a lower load. Although the crack deviated from the polished band for VIM, it did not occur until the crack reached a length of 8.5 mm. Thus, this dataset is deemed usable for further processing as sufficient data has been collected.

2.5 Data collection throughout the running experiment

The second objective of the experiment was to test the feasibility of data collection during the running experiment and to evaluate the performance of the proposed method on images taken without interrupting the test, as preferred by ASTM E647 [24]. This was accomplished using a synchronization device that monitored the

⁵ calculated as minimum force F_{min} divided by the maximum force F_{max} in the cycle

⁶ according to the known Paris curves of the materials in question to achieve reasonable crack growth rates

force readings from the testing machine. The device transmitted a triggering impulse to the camera at the moment of maximum force (when the crack was the most open) to capture an image every 100th cycle. Subsequently, only the first image after the ramp-up phase of the test was considered in creating the so-called dynamic dataset to achieve a representative comparison to the baseline.

3. Methods

To ensure clarity in explaining the implementation of the methods, the direction perpendicular to the expected crack path is referred to as y or vertical, while the direction along the crack path is x or horizontal. The origin of the coordinate system is at the notch tip, and the x -coordinate also represents the distance from the notch tip.

3.1 Visual inspection method as the baseline

The visual inspection method was implemented at the beginning of the data processing phase, even before knowing the results from the methods to be validated, to mitigate confirmation bias. The crack starting point on the notch edge, denoted as A_c , was identified once for each dataset (test), and its location was tracked throughout all images using DIC, with each image representing a pause in the experiment. The coordinates of the crack tips were assessed by a single person to ensure consistency, and all images within each dataset were evaluated collectively without unnecessary delays. Fig. 5 presents examples of the area around the crack tip for each material, with the crack tip marked in red.

Fig. 5 Examples of area around the crack tip (red mark) for each material

In the analysis of images to assess the crack tip position, it was considered that the resolution of the imaging system is inherently limited due to the effect of light diffraction and imperfections in the imaging system, which ultimately result in a certain degree of blurring of the crack tip. Additionally, the presence of various bright and dark vertical markings from grinding and polishing in the background made accurate determination of the crack tip's position more challenging due to reduced contrast when the crack tip was located in dimmer areas. To address these factors, a readout error interval for the crack tip's x coordinates was introduced.

This interval is derived from two points along the x-direction: the first point B_{cL} is located around the crack tip where its presence can be reliably determined (visible), while the second point B_{cR} is situated where the crack is no longer reliably present (visible). The length l_{ct} of the crack tip readout error interval is defined as the difference between their x-coordinates. A new point B_c is then established at the midpoint between B_{cL} and B_{cR} . The baseline crack length a_b is then calculated using the equation:

$$a_b = (x_{B_c} - x_{A_c}) \pm \frac{l_{ct}}{2} = a_{bm} \pm \delta_{cl} \quad (1)$$

where δ_{cl} represents the crack length assessment error. The middle crack length, a_{bm} , is derived by using the midpoint of the estimated readout error interval. The distribution of errors was positively skewed, and no general dependency of its value on the crack length was observed. Table 3 provides a statistical summary of the crack length assessment errors, including the maximum, minimum, mean, and standard deviation values, all rounded to the nearest half micron.

Table 3 Statistical summary of crack length assessment errors

<i>Material</i>	<i>Piece No.</i>	<i>min</i> δ_{cl} ^a [μm]	<i>mean</i> δ_{cl} [μm]	<i>std</i> ^b δ_{cl} [μm]	<i>max</i> δ_{cl} [μm]
38MnVS6	1	5.5	14.5	6.0	29.0
38MnVS6	2	5.0	14.0	5.5	28.0
1.4306	1	4.0	14.5	5.5	22.5
1.4306	2	6.0	14.0	6.0	24.0
1.4306	3	8.5	16.5	5.0	24.0
EN AW-7075	2	8.5	16.5	4.5	21.5

^a crack length assessment error

^b standard deviation

3.2 Image processing and data extraction

The deformations needed to be extracted from available images using DIC for the implementation of the IPM and DTM methods. For this purpose, the commercial software Alpha DIC from X-Sight was employed. Within the software, a set of line segments perpendicular to the crack path was defined. Each line segment was determined by its endpoints, whose changes in position were tracked between consecutive images by the DIC algorithm with subpixel accuracy. This enabled the calculation of the change in the length of the line segments, which therefore served as virtual extensometers (VE).

Fig. 6 (left) shows an illustration of the VE placement in the image of a cracked sample. A total of one thousand VE ($n_{ve} = 1000$) were used, spanning a total distance of $w_{ve} = 14.5 \text{ mm}$, referred to as the width of the virtual extensometers. The length of the VE was chosen to be $l_{ve} = 1.5 \text{ mm}$. This selection ensured that the entire correlation subset⁷ (also referred to as *subset*) included the pattern and was as close to the polished band as possible. The center point of each subset corresponds to the specific extreme point of the VE.

Fig. 6 Schematic illustration of the virtual extensometers (VE) placement in the image of cracked sample (left), and a detailed view of the utilized subset and underlying speckles (right)

The subset dimensions play an important role in the quality of DIC results. In this study, the subset formed a rectangle with a width w_{sub} (in the x -direction) and a height h_{sub} (in the y -direction). Choosing these dimensions required balancing between the advantages of a larger subset, which offers better measurement accuracy by capturing enough speckles for correlation and averaging the noise from the image acquisition process, and the benefits of a smaller subset, which enhances spatial resolution and reduces computational cost [67].

Fig. 6 (right) provides a detailed view of the utilized subset with the dimensions $w_{sub} = 21 \text{ px}$ and $h_{sub} = 81 \text{ px}$, along with the underlying speckle pattern. The small w_{sub} value ensures good spatial resolution in the x -direction where the crack tip's position is determined, while h_{sub} is considerably larger to capture enough distinctive features. Finally, the table 4 provides comprehensive overview of the experimental DIC settings and performance according to the [25].

⁷ is a set of pixels defined in the reference image in the proximity of the tracked point, which is used to determine its position in subsequent images

Table 4 Experimental DIC settings and performance (Alpha DIC software by X-Sight)

Technique used	2D image correlation
Subset size	21 x 81 pixel
Shift	68 pixel (84%)
Shape function	Affine and Perspective
Interpolation function	Yes (type not shared by developers)
Correlation criterion	Zero mean normalized sum of squared differences (ZNSSD)
Pre-smoothing applied to the images	None
Camera	12-bit, 4096 x 2160 pixel
Field of view	16.6 mm x 8.8 mm
Displacement resolution ^a	$\pm 0.04 \mu\text{m}$ or 0.01 pixel
Strain resolution ^b	$\pm 2.67 \times 10^{-5}$
^a according to [68]	
^b for $l_{ve} = 1.5 \text{ mm}$, which is the smallest length of virtual extensometers	

3.3 Strain threshold method as the benchmark

Building upon the deformation data, the DTM was implemented. It serves as the benchmark, representing the currently used 1D DIC evaluation approach in comparison with the proposed IPM. Specifically, its strain version is considered, which will be referred to as STM (strain threshold method). Strains were calculated from displacements by dividing the change in the length of each VE by its initial length. To further enhance the method's resolution, the strain threshold (S_{th}) was also compared to the linearly interpolated values between the discrete data points.

The main challenge in utilizing the STM lies in the correct determination of the S_{th} . Since exploring the correct S_{th} falls beyond the scope of this study, it was selected based on the results obtained by VIM, ensuring that the STM yields its best performance for the given dataset. Specifically, the selection criterion (referred to as the adjacency criterion) was based on the smallest sum of the least square differences between the predicted crack lengths by STM (a_{STM}) and the a_{bm} . Table 5 provides an overview of the S_{th} values that meet the adjacency criterion for each dataset (sample) and are used for further comparison.

Table 5 Overview of strain threshold values (S_{th}) that meet the adjacency criterion for each sample

Material	Piece No.	S_{th} [%]
38MnVS6	1	1.10
38MnVS6	2	0.90
1.4306	1	0.60
1.4306	2	0.65
1.4306	3	1.15
EN AW-7075	2	0.75

3.4 Regression approach for IPM

The resulting curves from the DIC, which serve as the input to the IPM, will be called COD projections (CODP). To construct the CODP, the change in length of VE was taken as a function of their distance from the notch. Additionally, the corresponding average value obtained within the crack ligament was subtracted from each point in the particular CODP. These curves qualitatively reflect the crack opening displacement on the crack faces, but they are not quantitatively identical, especially around the IP location where they should be described by the terms $r^{\frac{3}{2}}$ and $r^{\frac{1}{2}}$ introduced earlier. The shape of the CODP is influenced by numerous factors, such as the tested material, load level, l_{ve} , subset size, camera resolution, and optical system noise and distortions.

A regression method was needed to transform discrete data points from the CODP into a format suitable for identifying the location of the IP. For the reasons stated in the previous paragraph, methods requiring an explicit definition of the fitting formula were avoided, as well as polynomial regression, which requires choosing the polynomial order. Instead, emphasis was placed on a regression method with a low number of parameters, which produces a smooth derivative of the CODP, handles noisy data, and allows searching for the position of the IP at any location along the crack path.

Three potential regression methods were identified for further inspection: Savitzky-Golay filtering (SGF), support vector regression (SVR), and Gaussian process regression (GPR). SGF, based on local least-squares fitting of the data by polynomials, is a popular method for smoothing data and calculating derivatives of noisy data [69]. However, SGF's results are only available at existing CODP data points, requiring the placement of additional VE or the implementation of an additional interpolation procedure to achieve better spatial resolution. This limitation makes SGF less preferable than SVR and GPR.

On the other hand, SVR and GPR allow for sampling new points between available data points without requiring the selection of a specific interpolation procedure. Comparisons of SVR and GPR [70,71] showed that

GPR exhibits better performance, making it the most preferable candidate. Most importantly, GPR showed the most promising results when implementing and comparing the three identified methods on the actual data related to this work. Neural networks were also considered, but they were dismissed because GPR requires considerably fewer *hyperparameters*⁸ (also abbreviated as *hpars*) to perform the equivalent task, making it easier to analyze and optimize [72].

3.5 GPR principle

GPR is a kernel-based, nonparametric, probabilistic machine learning [73–75] method that models data using a gaussian process (GP), which is an infinite-dimensional generalization of the multivariate gaussian distribution (GD) [74]. Instead of defining a distribution for a finite set of points, GP defines a distribution over all possible functions that could fit the data. This is done by using two components: mean function and a covariance (kernel) function. The kernel function determines the correlation between input points, shaping the overall variability and smoothness of the functions modeled by the GP, while the mean function represents the average value at each point. The GPR implementation used in this work follows Algorithm 2.1 by Rasmussen and Williams [74].

Fig. 7 demonstrates the GPR principle and its application using an example that corresponds to the situation faced in this study. Consider a function with one real input x and one real output y :

$$f(x) = x \sin x \quad (2)$$

This function is depicted in Fig. 7 (left), along with the dataset of noiseless observations made on this function:

$$D = \{(\mathbf{X}_i, \mathbf{Y}_i), i = 1:M\} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{X} is a set of points at which the observation is performed, \mathbf{Y} is a set of observed values, and the M is the size of the dataset⁹. Using these observations, the GPR model was trained. Given that the GP is conceptualized as an infinite series of conditional GDs, each defined by a mean and variance that vary smoothly across x , predictions can be made at arbitrary points (green curve), including their 95% confidence intervals (green area). Fig. 7 (right) then shows two of these GDs at selected points x^* , highlighting the method's a probabilistic framework.

⁸ control the learning process of a machine learning model

⁹ meaning the CODP in one time point, considering the IPM context

Fig. 7 Example of Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) for noiseless observations of defined function (left) and resulting probability distributions of predicted points (right)

The commonly used kernel function for GPR is the radial basis function (RBF) [72], which is favored for its adaptivity, smoothness, and the infinite differentiability of the functions it generates. In cases involving noisy observations, such as the one addressed in this work, it is standard practice to include a white kernel, assuming that the noise present in all observations is independent and follows a normal distribution. The final kernel k in this work combines the RBF kernel and the white kernel (k_w):

$$k(x, x') = \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2H_{ls}^2} (x - x')^2 \right] + k_w(x, x'), \quad k_w(x, x') \begin{cases} H_{nl} & \text{for } x = x' \\ 0 & \text{for } x \neq x' \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where H_{ls} is a hyperparameter known as the length scale, which determines the expected similarity between neighboring points and controls the maximum value of the first derivative of the functions within the kernel. The hyperparameter H_{nl} , called the noise level, defines the variance of the present noise. These hyperparameters are optimized each time GPR is trained on new observations, in this case for each CODP curve, which particularly enhances the versatility of the IPM.

Unlike neural networks, which require large datasets to train a model that generalizes to unseen data, the generalization in GPR comes from an infinite set of smooth functions that can be used to fit the observed data at any given moment. In this study, the learning process is ongoing, with hyperparameters continuously updated as new measurements (data points) are collected. In this way, the model constantly adapts to the evolving nature of the underlying relationship, offering the desired versatility, robustness, and accuracy.

In this context, the hyperparameters in GPR, which ensure that the selected functions best fit the observed data, take on a slightly different role compared to their traditional use in machine learning (such as in neural networks). Here, they function more like model parameters that are "trained" during the learning process. However, the term "hyperparameters" is retained to maintain consistency with the general terminology.

The optimization is performed using the L-BFGS-B (limited memory Broyden–Fletcher–Goldfarb–Shanno algorithm variant for constrained optimization [76]) with the logarithm of the marginal likelihood as the objective function to maximize [77]. The kernel function is used to calculate covariance matrices:

$$\mathbf{K} = [k(X_i, X_j)]_{i=1:M, j=1:M} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_* = [k(X_i, x^*)]_{i=1:M} \quad (6)$$

Assuming the \mathbf{Y} is normalized to zero mean, the model's predicted value y^* for x^* over D is calculated according to Bayes' theorem as:

$$y^* = \mathbf{K}_*^T \mathbf{K}^{-1} \mathbf{Y} \quad (7)$$

3.6 Inflection point method

Building upon this foundation of GPR, the IPM algorithm proposed by the authors comprises three main phases. The individual phases, along with the conditions, corrections, parameters, and hyperparameters, will be discussed in the following text.

In the first phase (P1), also known as GPR global, regression is performed on the entire CODP. If this is the first CODP in a given measurement, the optimization is restarted ten times with randomly initialized hyperparameters to explore as much of the design space as possible. For subsequent CODP curves, the optimization runs only once, using the optimal hyperparameters from the previous P1 GPR as the initial guess. This approach assumes that successive CODP will not vary significantly, resulting in minimal changes in the hyperparameters, thus enhancing the computational efficiency of the optimization process.

The hyperparameters design space was proposed based on the resulting hyperparameter values from the IPM application on both static and dynamic datasets, as illustrated in the Fig. 8. Specifically, the lower and upper bounds for the length scale and the noise level were set to:

$$H_{ls} = (H_{ls,l}, H_{ls,u}) = (0.3, 3) \text{ mm} \quad (8)$$

$$H_{nl} = (H_{nl,l}, H_{nl,u}) = (10^{-6}, 10^{-1}) \text{ mm}^2 \quad (9)$$

Fig. 8 Values of GPR hyperparameters from the static and dynamic datasets

Performing the GPR on a CODP originating from thousand VE proved to be very time-consuming, so attention was paid to determining the appropriate number of points. From the investigation of GPR prediction results and computation times, it was determined to consider every n^{th} point from the original CODP points, where this parameter, referred to as the global data decimation level, equals 10. Thus, the computational time was significantly reduced while preserving the accuracy of the method.

To further enhance the accuracy of the IPM, additional phases were introduced to address the challenges encountered during the initial regression attempts. Specifically, it was observed that the GPR global could not adequately capture the IP in certain cases due to the sharp transition between the convex and concave regions. One of these cases is exemplified in Fig. 9. This limitation necessitated the introduction of phase 2 (P2), called GPR localization, where the regression is performed only for the data in the localization interval:

$$I = \langle x_{ip1} - 0.2w_{ve}, x_{ip1} + 0.2w_{ve} \rangle \quad (10)$$

Here, x_{ip1} is the predicted location of the IP from P1 and the value of 0.2 is referred to as localization interval factor (F_{li}). Additionally, the local data decimation level, denoted as m , was chosen in the same way as n in P1.

Fig. 9 Example of training data from DIC and GPR global predictions; detail of the sharp transition around the inflection point, which is not properly captured; for EN AW-7075 No. 2 sample

This localized approach provided overall better results than the GPR global. However, the results were still not entirely satisfactory, especially for shorter cracks up to approximately 2.5 mm, primarily due to the low CODP values and the influence of higher loads used for crack initiation. In some of these instances, the most distinctive IP was identified very close to the notch tip, i.e., at crack lengths lower than 0.5 mm. Therefore, corrective actions were introduced for cases that fulfill Condition 1, which was formulated as:

$$x_{ip1} < 1 \text{ mm} \quad (11)$$

The corrections varied in the following two cases. When the algorithm processed the first CODP, Correction 1 increased the F_{li} by 0.1. Correction 2 was then applied for all subsequent iterations, with the corrected interval for GPR localization defined as:

$$I_{C2} = < a_{IPM,i-1} - 0.2w_{ve}, a_{IPM,i-1} + 0.2w_{ve} > \quad (12)$$

where i is the ordinal number of current iteration (time point) and $a_{IPM,i-1}$ is the resulting crack length from the previous iteration.

Examination of outliers in the results of IPM revealed that, in certain cases, the region for the P2 contained two fairly distinct IP, which contradicted the assumed shape of the CODP. To resolve these cases, an additional phase 3 (P3), referred to as GPR smoothing, was introduced and is activated when Condition 2 is not met. Condition 2 consists of two parts. The first part checks for the absence of another IP in front of the most prominent one by using the second derivative of the P2 GPR. The second part has two implications: it ensures that there is no over-smoothing and it expresses a preference for P2, potentially P3 results over the P1 ones. This part can be expressed as:

$$0.75 \text{ CODP}'_{P1}(x_{ip1}) > [\text{CODP}'_{P2}(x_{ip2}) \text{ or } \text{CODP}'_{P3}(x_{ip3})] \quad (13)$$

where a value of 0.75 can be referred to as the *derivative distinction factor* (F_{dd}).

As far as the P3 process itself is concerned, the only difference from P2 is the lower bound for the length scale value, which is defined as follows:

$$H_{ls,l}^{P3} = \frac{H_{ls,opt}^{P2} + H_{ls,opt}^{P1}}{2} \quad (14)$$

where $H_{ls,opt}^{P2}$ and $H_{ls,opt}^{P1}$ are the optimal values of the length scale obtained from P2 and P1, respectively. This adjustment prevents the resulting function from adapting too closely to the underlying data, achieving the desired smoothing effect. Only one smoothing is allowed ($n_s = 1$). For hyperparameters optimization, both P2 and P3 use the optimal values from P1 as the initial guess.

If the results after smoothing do not meet Condition 2, the area used for GPR localization is halved using the interval decrement factor ($F_{id} = 2$), and P2 and possibly P3 are repeated. The algorithm allows for only one halving; if Condition 2 is still not met, the x_{ip1} is considered to be the resulting crack length a_{IPM} .

The overview of the entire process of determining the a_{IPM} from the CODP is depicted in Fig. 10. This figure illustrates individual sub-processes, decision-making, as well as the flow of some important values in their interrelationships.

Fig. 10 Inflection point method flowchart, including individual sub-processes, decision-making (conditions), corrections, and the flow of important values (mainly considering the hyperparameters) as described in the subsection 3.6

4. Sensitivity analysis

In this chapter, the effect of various parameters on the performance and robustness of the IPM was studied. The analysis was divided into three parts: variables in the image processing part, parameters within the IPM algorithm, and test variables, with only load levels presented in this chapter. The remaining two test variables, material and sample width, are elaborated on in the Results (section 5) and Discussion (section 6). First, let's start with the metrics.

4.1 Metrics definition

Three popular error measures from the field of machine learning regression [78] were chosen to evaluate the deviations of the method's final results from the baseline in the sensitivity analysis and in the overall performance comparison of the IPM and STM: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). MAE and RMSE are defined as follows: [79]:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |a_{IPM,i} - g_i| \quad (15)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (a_{IPM,i} - g_i)^2} \quad (16)$$

where N is the number of time points in the dataset, and g_i is the readout error-corrected baseline value at a particular time point:

$$g_i = \min(|a_{IPM,i} - (a_{bm,i} + \delta_{cl,i})|, |a_{IPM,i} - (a_{bm,i} - \delta_{cl,i})|) \quad (17)$$

MAPE is defined similarly:

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{a_{IPM,i} - g_i}{g_i} \right| \quad (18)$$

For comparisons, a summary metric called the Loss function (\mathcal{L}) was introduced, which combines the aforementioned three metrics. RMSE was included alongside the MAE due to its sensitivity to outliers, and MAPE was added to account for relative errors, as the proposed method operates over a relatively wide range of crack lengths. The \mathcal{L} is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{3} MAE_{norm} + \frac{1}{3} RMSE_{norm} + \frac{1}{3} MAPE_{norm} = \frac{1}{3} \frac{MAE}{MAE_{IPMs}} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{RMSE}{RMSE_{IPMs}} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{MAPE}{MAPE_{IPMs}} \quad (19)$$

where the subscript "norm" indicates that the metrics are normalized to their corresponding values from the IPM application on the static dataset (IPMs).

4.2 Parameters related to DIC

From the parameters related to the image correlation part of the process, l_{ve} and the size of the correlation subset were studied. Fig. 11 (left) illustrates the influence of changing the l_{ve} from the 1.5 up to 2.5 mm on the normalized metrics (\mathcal{L} , MAE_{norm} , $RMSE_{norm}$, $MAPE_{norm}$). The trends suggest that increasing the l_{ve} initially leads to an increase in the number of outliers, indicated by higher $RMSE_{norm}$ values compared to MAE_{norm} . This effect is observed up to $l_{ve} = 1.8\text{ mm}$, beyond which the overall accuracy deteriorates. This identifies the l_{ve} as a very influential parameter.

Fig. 11 Relationship between normalized metrics values and the length of virtual extensometers for static dataset (left), and dimensions of the correlation subset (right)

The effect of the correlation subset size, specifically its width (w_{sub}) and height (h_{sub}), on the normalized metrics is shown in the Fig. 11 (right). The results indicate that very small correlation subsets perform poorly due to insufficient features capture. As the subset area increases, performance improves significantly, especially with increased h_{sub} compared to w_{sub} . This confirms that a taller, narrower rectangular subset provides better IPM performance by enhancing spatial resolution in the crack growth direction. Further increases in subset area do not significantly impact performance, as the \mathcal{L} values remain below 1.25, but computational time increases. Therefore, the chosen subset dimensions of $(w_{sub}, h_{sub}) = (21, 81)\text{ px}$, as detailed in the Image processing and data extraction subsection (3.2), are appropriate for both accuracy and computational time.

4.3 Parameters related to IPM

Next, the influence of parameters introduced in the IPM algorithm was analyzed. First, global and local data decimation levels (n and m), which are important for reducing computation time, were tested. Fig. 12 (left) highlights the impact of these parameters on results of the proposed method. The method is generally not very sensitive within the selected intervals of parameters, as the \mathcal{L} does not exceed a value of 1.3 - except when

$m < 5$, where the results degrade sharply due to GPR overfitting. Overall, for the parameter n , a slight deterioration of the results is observed, caused by a rise in the number of outliers due to over-decimation of the data. A similar situation occurs when increasing m above 7.

Fig. 12 Relationship between normalized metrics and the global and local data decimation levels (n , m) (left), and the number of smoothings and derivative distinction factor (n_s , F_{dd}) (middle), and the interval decrement factor and localization interval factor (F_{id} , F_{li}) (right)

Next, the influence of the F_{dd} along with n_s was investigated. For this analysis, the lower bound of the length scale used in the P3 was derived using the following generalization of Eq. (14):

$$H_{ls,i}^{P3} = H_{ls,opt}^{P1} + \frac{i(H_{ls,opt}^{P1} - H_{ls,opt}^{P2})}{n_s}; \quad i = 1; n_s; n_s \in \mathbb{N} \quad (20)$$

The satisfaction of Condition 2 was checked after each smoothing iteration. The tested interval also included $n_s = 0$, meaning that P3 did not run at all. The results shown in the Fig. 12 (middle) indicate that the n_s affects the results minimally when smoothing is applied. Without smoothing ($n_s = 0$), the number of outliers slightly increase, especially for longer cracks. Higher F_{dd} values, emphasizing phase P1 over P2, significantly increase outliers, starting with longer cracks and then affecting shorter ones as well.

Last, the effect of F_{li} and F_{id} , which determine the length of the I used for GPR in the P2 and P3, was assessed. Fig. 12 (right) reveals that the method is almost insensitive to changes in F_{id} between 1.5 and 3. However, when $F_{id} = 1$, meaning that repeating P2 and P3 with a smaller area for GPR is not allowed, there is a noticeable worsening of the results, especially for short cracks. Similarly, a low value of the F_{li} accompanies a deterioration in result due to the increase in the number of outliers. In the rest of the tested interval, no significant effect is observed.

4.4 Load level dependency

To further assess the effect of the load level, additional procedure was added into the test of the EN AW-7075 No. 2 sample. In the several readouts, the static load was incrementally increased in five consecutive steps up to 5kN, as illustrated in Fig. 13. Thus, four load dependencies at the constant crack lengths were created. In these

cases, the specified 33% of the static overload was deliberately exceeded to assess the method's performance across a broader range of loads.

Fig. 13 Schematic illustration of the load increase during the load increment readout phases for the EN AW-7075 No. 2 sample

It turned out that although the IPM results have some dependence on the load level, this dependence is significantly smaller than for the STM, as shown in Fig. 14. For instance, for a crack length of 5.5 mm and a load level of 1 kN, the STM estimates that the crack is not present, while the IPM gives a value of 5.28 mm. This indicates an incomparably higher robustness and versatility of the proposed method.

Fig. 14 Results of the methods comparison in terms of load dependency for the four different load increment readout phases during the aluminum alloy No. 2 sample testing

5. Results

The results in the methods comparison presented in this chapter are expressed as differences from the baseline crack lengths (Δ_{bm} , Δ_{IPMs} , Δ_{IPMd} , Δ_{STM}) as a function of the of baseline crack length a_{bm} for each CT sample. These differences correspond to the results of the VIM, the IPMs, the IPM applied to the dynamic dataset (IPMd), and the STM applied to the static dataset, respectively. The values are defined as:

$$\Delta_j = a_j - a_{bm}; j \in \{bm, IPMs, IPMd, STM\} \quad (21)$$

Additionally, along with the Δ_{bm} values, the band $\pm\delta_{cl}$ is depicted.

This approach to plotting emphasizes the differences in results between the methods, which would not be as noticeable if the crack lengths were shown directly on the y-axis. For the x-axis, if the number of cycles were

used, the points would be unevenly distributed in the graph because a significantly higher number of cycles pass between readouts for shorter cracks compared to longer cracks. By using the baseline crack length, the points are more evenly distributed in the graph, making the situation clearer.

Figs. 15-17 show the comparison of the methods for specific groups of materials: low-alloy steel, stainless steel, and aluminum alloy, respectively. In all of these figures, the most noticeable are the curves for STM, which display an approximately linear trend in deviating from the correct values. This indicates the crack length dependency of the STM results.

Fig. 15 Methods comparison in terms of their differences from the baseline as the function of baseline crack length for the low-alloy steel sample No.1 (top) and No.2 (bottom)

Fig. 16 Methods comparison in terms of their differences from the baseline as the function of baseline crack length for the stainless-steel sample No.1, No.2 and No.3

Fig. 17 Methods comparison in terms of their differences from the baseline as the function of baseline crack length for the aluminum alloy sample No.2

On the other hand, the results of the proposed method do not deviate from the baseline results but instead oscillate around them. In the case of IPM application to the dynamic dataset, an increased number of outliers is

observed; however, overall, the results can be considered correct. The increase in the number of outliers can also be inferred from the higher RMSE to MAE ratio (1.43) compared to the ratio for the static dataset (1.29), calculated from the RMSE and MAE values presented in Table 6. The table summarizes the overall results of the different methods applied in this study, highlighting the key performance metrics.

In terms of relative errors, they tend to decline with increasing crack length for the IPM. Conversely, this is not true for the STM, where the absolute error increases as the crack length grows. Depending on the rate of absolute error growth compared to crack growth, the relative error for STM might, at best, decline more slowly than for IPM, but it could also remain the same or even increase.

Table 6						Summary of
overall						results for
particular		MAE [μm]	RMSE [μm]	MAPE [%]	\mathcal{L} [-]	methods
	IPMs	24	31	0.50	1.0	Overall, provides results agreement with
	IPMd	54	77	1.15	2.3	
the IPM	STM	215	274	5.43	10.8	
in good						

the baseline for both the static and dynamic datasets, although its accuracy is approximately 2.3 times worse for the dynamic dataset compared to the static one. In contrast, the STM results for the static dataset are 10.8 times worse than those of the IPM. Regarding the IPM dependency on the selected material and sample thickness, no significant qualitative or quantitative differences in the method's results have been observed.

6. Discussion

The validation of the IPM and the inflection point principle on a static dataset is deemed successful, as its results correspond reasonably well to the baseline. Additionally, the feasibility of measuring and applying the proposed method during a running experiment (dynamic dataset) was effectively demonstrated. Although the method achieves lower accuracy with the dynamic dataset, the results remain correct.

The robustness and versatility of the IPM with respect to test variables have been shown, particularly regarding changes in the load level. This is crucial because load levels are commonly adjusted during standard tests to obtain crack growth rates for different values of the SIF. This advantage of the IPM is even more evident in contrast to the results of the STM, not only in the presented sensitivity analysis but also in light of the various S_{th} values (Table 5) utilized in the methods comparison.

No dependency has been observed either in terms of different materials or sample thickness. It is reasonable to assume that the method will perform equivalently with different metallic materials, sample sizes,

or even sample types, as it implements a regression technique that easily adjusts to the specific nature of data in each experiment, thanks to continual learning throughout the test. For example, it adjusts to the noise level or the character of the CODP curve around the inflection point without user intervention. The IPM is recommended only for metallic materials, as the inflection point principle has not been validated for other materials such as composites or plastics. Future research will cover different sample types, including the MT (middle tension) sample type.

Regarding the parameters related to the DIC setup, l_{ve} significantly affects the IPM outcomes. The current results suggest that shorter lengths are better, but it was not possible to test l_{ve} smaller than 1.5 mm due to the nature of the validation experiment. However, smaller values could improve the accuracy of the method, assuming the propagating crack remains outside the regions included in the correlation subsets throughout the entire experiment. This assumption will be tested in future research.

In terms of the subset size, it is advisable to have a smaller dimension in the direction of crack propagation. The specific values will depend on the speckle size and density in the image, which are influenced by the hardware, particularly the camera resolution and telecentric lens magnification, as well as the actual realization of the speckles on the specimen. Therefore, it is advisable to follow the general rules for subset size selection outlined in the Image processing and data extraction subsection (3.2).

The parameters directly related to the IPM were always chosen to balance the method's accuracy and computational time. The sensitivity analysis in terms of F_{id}, F_{li} indicates that the IPM can be used for $w_{ve} = \langle 10.0, 14.5 \rangle mm$ without noticeably affecting its performance. This provides flexibility in selecting the telecentric lens and machine vision camera. Based on the analysis of n and m , their final values are set to $n = 2$ and $m = 1$. The recommended spatial frequency of VE, $f_{ve} = \langle 11, 14 \rangle mm^{-1}$, should be used to determine n_{ve} . This is obtained from the product of w_{ve} and the selected f_{ve} within the recommended intervals, ensuring that the user's setup matches the tested settings.

Applicability limits for real-time measurements were tested using for $w_{ve} = 14.5 mm$ using $n_{ve} = 200$, corresponding to a value from the upper part of the f_{ve} interval. This setup resulted in 34 ms for data extraction from the image¹⁰ and 101 ms for the IPM computations¹¹. Hardware operations like chip exposure and reading take approximately 15 ms. Considering that hardware operations and DIC for the current frame run in parallel with the IPM calculation for the previous frame, this allows for 10 FPS. For a sample loading frequency between

¹⁰ using parallelized computation on a 4-cores (as it is supposed that this number of cores could be available on the majority of lab computers) of AMD Ryzen 9 5950X processor at a clock rate 4.2 GHz.

¹¹ utilizing serial computation on one core of the processor at a clock rate 4.2 GHz

60-90 Hz, it enables processing every 6th to 9th load cycle. Potential improvements in the computational time of IPM, which is currently the bottleneck of the process, will be explored in future research. Significant improvements could be achieved through parallelization of specific parts of the process.

However, there are certain challenges and limitations. For crack lengths smaller than 1.5 mm, the IPM did not provide accurate results due to the relatively low values of measured influenced by noise-induced errors in the DIC and the impact of higher forces present during crack initiation on the area around the notch tip. Furthermore, the IPM is more computationally intensive compared to the STM, resulting in a noticeably lower FPS, which could potentially pose a barrier to its use. It is also not recommended to use the IPM for cracks longer than $(w_{ve} - 0.5) \text{ mm}$, as the method requires the presence of data on both sides of the inflection point.

Further research will focus on applying the IPM to measure and evaluate fatigue crack growth rates without stopping the test, emphasizing the reduction of outliers, which have been identified as a major factor affecting accuracy in this study. Additionally, the aforementioned issues will be addressed.

7. Conclusion

The VIM is a widely used non-contact approach for measuring crack lengths in fatigue tests. However, it requires stopping the test and the presence of an operator to evaluate the current crack length, making it very inefficient. Existing approaches utilizing DIC offer potential solutions to improve this process. Full-field 2D/3D DIC measurements are computationally demanding, and the application of DTM/STM is challenging due to the difficulty in determining the correct threshold value, which depends mainly on the applied load level, but also on the tested material or sample size.

This study aimed to address the identified research gap by proposing a novel non-contact, physically-based approach for real-time crack length measurement in fatigue tests of metals, called IPM. The IPM, which uses the inflection point principle, DIC, and machine learning, is designed to be relatively computationally efficient and accurate. Most importantly, it eliminates the need for threshold values, enables crack length assessment without stopping the test, and paves the way for greater automation of the testing process, usable for example in the adaptive testing strategies.

The IPM and its underlying principle were successfully validated using an unprecedented approach that allowed the application of both DIC and VIM on the same side of the CT sample. The feasibility of its use during a running experiment was demonstrated in terms of data collection, real-time evaluation, and accuracy, yielding satisfactory results. The conducted sensitivity study has shown the robustness of the method to various parameters, particularly to variations in the load level. Additionally, user recommendations for practical

implementation of the IPM were formulated. Finally, a comparison with the thresholding approach was presented, indicating that the thresholding approach achieves much worse accuracy than IPM and its outcomes are significantly load-dependent.

The proposed method already extends the applicability of the existing 1D DIC approach to fatigue testing of metals due to its versatility, robustness, and accuracy, enabling a greater level of automation in fatigue testing and laying the groundwork for further research in this area.

Acknowledgements

The research leading to these results received funding from Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research under project number CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634.

This work is an output of the project Computational modelling of ductile fracture of identical wrought and printed metallic materials under ultra-low-cycle fatigue created with financial support from the Czech Science Foundation under the registration no. 23-04724S.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at <https://zenodo.org> under DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14770279

Competing interests

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose other than those stated in the Acknowledgements section.

References

- [1] A. Wöhler, Versuche über die Festigkeit der Eisenbahnwagenachsen, Zeitschrift Für Bauwesen 10 (1860) 160–161.
- [2] D. Kirkaldy, Results of an experimental inquiry into the tensile strength and other properties of various kinds of wrought-iron and steel By David Kirkaldy, Printed for and sold by the author, 1866, England, 1866.
- [3] A. Wöhler, Über die Festigkeitsversuche mit Eisen und Stahl, Zeitschrift Für Bauwesen 20 (1870) 73–106.

- [4] G. Charpy, Note sur l'Essai des Métaux à la Flexion par Choc de Barreaux En-taillés, (Note on High Rate Flexion Testing of Notched Metal Bars), Mémoires et Comptes-Rendus de La Sociétés Ingénieurs Civils de France (1901).
- [5] G. Charpy, Sur l'Essai des Metaux par Flexion de Barreaux Entaillés (The Testing of Metals by the Flexion of Notched Bars), Memoires de La Sociétés Ingénieurs Civils de France (1904).
- [6] C.E. Inglis, Stresses in a plate due to the presence of cracks and sharp corners, Proc Inst Naval Arch 55 (1913) 219–230.
- [7] A.A. Griffith, The phenomena of rupture and flow in solids, England, 1920.
- [8] A. Griffith, The theory of rupture, Proc First Int Congr Appl Mech (1924) 55–63.
- [9] G.R. Irwin, Fracture dynamics. Fracturing of metals, American Society for Metals (1948) 147–166.
- [10] G.R. Irwin, Analysis of Stresses and Strains Near the End of a Crack Traversing a Plate, J Appl Mech 24 (1957) 361–364.
- [11] E. Orowan, Fracture and strength of solids, Reports on Progress in Physics 12 (1949) 185–232.
- [12] A. Wells, Unstable crack propagation in metals: cleavage and fast fracture, in: Proceedings of the Crack Propagation Symposium, 1961: p. 26028.
- [13] J.R. Rice, A Path Independent Integral and the Approximate Analysis of Strain Concentration by Notches and Cracks, J Appl Mech 35 (1968) 379–386.
- [14] P.C. Paris, The growth of cracks due to variations in load, Lehigh University, 1962.
- [15] G.R. Irwin, J.A. Kies, Critical energy rate analysis of fracture strength, Spie Milestone Series MS 137 (1997) 136–141.
- [16] A. Saxena, S.J. Hudak Jr, Review and extension of compliance information for common crack growth specimens, Int J Fract 14 (1978) 453–468.
- [17] G. Wilkowski, W. Maxey, Review and applications of the electric potential method for measuring crack growth in specimens, flawed pipes, and pressure vessels, in: Fourteenth National Symposium on Fracture Mechanics, 2020: pp. 266–294.
- [18] D.R. Donaldson, W.E. Anderson, Crack propagation behavior of some airframe materials, in: Proceedings of the Crack Propagation Symposium, 1961: pp. 375–441.
- [19] P.C. Paris, B.R. Hayden, A new system for fatigue crack growth measurement and control, in: ASTM Symposium on Fatigue Crack Growth, 1979.

- [20] J.E. Srawley, W.F. Brown, Fracture toughness testing, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, 1965.
- [21] A.M. Sullivan, T.W. Crooker, A crack-opening-displacement technique for crack length measurement in fatigue crack growth rate testing—development and evaluation, *Eng Fract Mech* 9 (1977) 159–166.
- [22] R.J. Bucci, P.C. Paris, R.W. Hertzberg, R.A. Schmidt, A.F. Anderson, Fatigue threshold crack propagation in air and dry argon for a Ti-6Al-4V alloy, *ASTM STP 513* (1972) 125–140.
- [23] P. Pokorný, T. Vojtek, L. Náhlík, P. Hutař, Crack closure in near-threshold fatigue crack propagation in railway axle steel EA4T, *Eng Fract Mech* 185 (2017) 2–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2017.02.013>.
- [24] ASTM International, ASTM E647-23a: Standard Test Method for Measurement of Fatigue Crack Growth Rates, (2023) 1–52.
- [25] International Digital Image Correlation Society, E.M.C. Jones, M.A. Iadicola, A Good Practices Guide for Digital Image Correlation, (2018). <https://doi.org/10.32720/idics/gpg.ed1>.
- [26] M.A. Sutton, W.J. Wolters, W.H. Peters, W.F. Ranson, S.R. McNeill, Determination of displacements using an improved digital correlation method, *Image Vis Comput* 1 (1983) 133–139.
- [27] J. Zhao, Y. Sang, F. Duan, The state of the art of two-dimensional digital image correlation computational method, *Engineering Reports* 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1002/eng2.12038>.
- [28] H. Schreier, J.-J. Orteu, M.A. Sutton, *Image Correlation for Shape, Motion and Deformation Measurements*, Springer US, Boston, MA, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-78747-3>.
- [29] Teledyne FLIR LLC, Blackfly S USB3, (2023). <https://www.flir.com/products/blackfly-s-usb3/> (accessed November 16, 2023).
- [30] J. Zhao, Y. Sang, F. Duan, The state of the art of two-dimensional digital image correlation computational method, *Engineering Reports* 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1002/eng2.12038>.
- [31] J. Abanto-Bueno, J. Lambros, Investigation of crack growth in functionally graded materials using digital image correlation, *Eng Fract Mech* 69 (2002) 1695–1711. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-7944\(02\)00058-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-7944(02)00058-9).
- [32] J.R. Yates, M. Zanganeh, Y.H. Tai, Quantifying crack tip displacement fields with DIC, *Eng Fract Mech* 77 (2010) 2063–2076. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2010.03.025>.
- [33] F. Mathieu, F. Hild, S. Roux, Identification of a crack propagation law by digital image correlation, *Int J Fatigue* 36 (2012) 146–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2011.08.004>.

- [34] J.M. Vasco-Olmo, F.A. Díaz, Experimental evaluation of plasticity-induced crack shielding from crack tip displacements fields, *Frattura Ed Integrità Strutturale* 9 (2015) 191–198. <https://doi.org/10.3221/IGF-ESIS.33.24>.
- [35] J. Réthoré, F. Hild, S. Roux, Extended digital image correlation with crack shape optimization, *Int J Numer Methods Eng* 73 (2008) 248–272. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.2070>.
- [36] S. Roux, J. Réthoré, F. Hild, Digital image correlation and fracture: an advanced technique for estimating stress intensity factors of 2D and 3D cracks, *J Phys D Appl Phys* 42 (2009) 214004. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/42/21/214004>.
- [37] E. Fagerholt, E. Østby, T. Børvik, O.S. Hopperstad, Investigation of fracture in small-scale SENT tests of a welded X80 pipeline steel using Digital Image Correlation with node splitting, *Eng Fract Mech* 96 (2012) 276–293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2012.08.007>.
- [38] E. Durif, M. Fregonese, J. Rethore, A. Combescure, Development of a Digital Image Correlation controlled fatigue crack propagation experiment, *EPJ Web Conf* 6 (2010) 31012. <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/20100631012>.
- [39] S. Vanlanduit, J. Vanherzeele, R. Longo, P. Guillaume, A digital image correlation method for fatigue test experiments, *Opt Lasers Eng* 47 (2009) 371–378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlaseng.2008.03.016>.
- [40] P. López-Crespo, R.L. Burguete, E.A. Patterson, A. Shterenlikht, P.J. Withers, J.R. Yates, Study of a Crack at a Fastener Hole by Digital Image Correlation, *Exp Mech* 49 (2009) 551–559. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11340-008-9161-1>.
- [41] D. Chen, S. Sun, J.M. Dulieu-Barton, Q. Li, W. Wang, Crack growth analysis in welded and non-welded T-joints based on lock-in digital image correlation and thermoelastic stress analysis, *Int J Fatigue* 110 (2018) 172–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2018.01.020>.
- [42] J.M. Vasco-Olmo, F.A. Díaz, F.V. Antunes, M.N. James, Characterisation of fatigue crack growth using digital image correlation measurements of plastic CTOD, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics* 101 (2019) 332–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tafmec.2019.03.009>.
- [43] J.D. Carroll, W. Abuzaid, J. Lambros, H. Sehitoglu, High resolution digital image correlation measurements of strain accumulation in fatigue crack growth, *Int J Fatigue* 57 (2013) 140–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2012.06.010>.

- [44] S.Y. Alam, A. Loukili, F. Grondin, Monitoring size effect on crack opening in concrete by digital image correlation, *European Journal of Environmental and Civil Engineering* 16 (2012) 818–836. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19648189.2012.672211>.
- [45] W. Dong, Z. Wu, X. Zhou, N. Wang, G. Kastiukas, An experimental study on crack propagation at rock-concrete interface using digital image correlation technique, *Eng Fract Mech* 171 (2017) 50–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2016.12.003>.
- [46] B. Omondi, D.G. Aggelis, H. Sol, C. Sitters, Improved crack monitoring in structural concrete by combined acoustic emission and digital image correlation techniques, *Struct Health Monit* 15 (2016) 359–378. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1475921716636806>.
- [47] G. Ruocci, C. Rospars, G. Moreau, P. Bisch, S. Erlicher, A. Delaplace, J. -M. Henault, Digital Image Correlation and Noise-filtering Approach for the Cracking Assessment of Massive Reinforced Concrete Structures, *Strain* 52 (2016) 503–521. <https://doi.org/10.1111/str.12192>.
- [48] E. Mündecke, V. Mechtcherine, Tensile behaviour of strain-hardening cement-based composites (SHCC) with steel reinforcing bars, *Cem Concr Compos* 105 (2020) 103423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2019.103423>.
- [49] N. Gehri, J. Mata-Falcón, W. Kaufmann, Automated crack detection and measurement based on digital image correlation, *Constr Build Mater* 256 (2020) 119383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.119383>.
- [50] A. Rezaie, R. Achanta, M. Godio, K. Beyer, Comparison of crack segmentation using digital image correlation measurements and deep learning, *Constr Build Mater* 261 (2020) 120474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.120474>.
- [51] A. Gosch, J. Geier, F. Arbeiter, M. Berer, G. Pinter, Methods for automated crack length detection in fracture mechanical fatigue tests of unreinforced polymers, *Procedia Structural Integrity* 28 (2020) 1184–1192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2020.11.100>.
- [52] C.M. Stewart, E. Garcia, Fatigue crack growth of a hot mix asphalt using digital image correlation, *Int J Fatigue* 120 (2019) 254–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2018.11.024>.
- [53] S. Rabbolini, S. Beretta, S. Foletti, Fatigue crack growth in low cycle fatigue: an analysis of crack closure based on image correlation, *Procedia Structural Integrity* 1 (2016) 158–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2016.02.022>.

- [54] M. Besel, E. Breitbarth, Advanced analysis of crack tip plastic zone under cyclic loading, *Int J Fatigue* 93 (2016) 92–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2016.08.013>.
- [55] Imetrum, Crack Length Gauge: identifying the threshold value for DCB specimens, 2022. <https://support.imetrum.com/support/solutions/articles/80001044765-crack-length-gauge-identifying-the-threshold-value-for-dcb-specimens> (accessed December 2, 2023).
- [56] X-Sight, ALPHA DIC SOFTWARE MODULES: CRACK PROBE, (2022). <https://www.xsight.eu/alpha-digital-image-correlation-software-modules/#CL> (accessed December 2, 2023).
- [57] G.I. Barenblatt, The Mathematical Theory of Equilibrium Cracks in Brittle Fracture, *Advances in Applied Mechanics* 7 (1962) 55–129. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2156\(08\)70121-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2156(08)70121-2).
- [58] D.S. Dugdale, Yielding of steel sheets containing slits, *J Mech Phys Solids* 8 (1960) 100–104. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5096\(60\)90013-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5096(60)90013-2).
- [59] J.J. Zhang, Chapter 4 - Basic rock fracture mechanics, in: J.J. Zhang (Ed.), *Applied Petroleum Geomechanics*, Gulf Professional Publishing, 2019: pp. 133–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814814-3.00004-6>.
- [60] H. Askes, E.C. Aifantis, Gradient elasticity in statics and dynamics: An overview of formulations, length scale identification procedures, finite element implementations and new results, *Int J Solids Struct* 48 (2011) 1962–1990. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2011.03.006>.
- [61] G. Sciarra, S. Vidoli, Asymptotic Fracture Modes in Strain-Gradient Elasticity: Size Effects and Characteristic Lengths for Isotropic Materials, *J Elast* 113 (2013) 27–53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10659-012-9409-y>.
- [62] P. Skalka, P. Navrátil, M. Kotoul, Novel approach to FE solution of crack problems in the Laplacian-based gradient elasticity, *Mechanics of Materials* 95 (2016) 28–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mechmat.2015.12.007>.
- [63] T. L. Anderson, *Fracture Mechanics: Fundamentals and Applications*, Third Edition, 3rd ed., CRC Press, 2005.
- [64] M. Kotoul, P. Skalka, T. Profant, M. Friák, P. Řehák, P. Šesták, M. Černý, J. Pokluda, Ab initio aided strain gradient elasticity theory in prediction of nanocomponent fracture, *Mechanics of Materials* 136 (2019) 103074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mechmat.2019.103074>.

- [65] B. Ščerba, T. Adamec, Návrat Tomáš, VALIDATION OF CRACK LENGTH MEASUREMENT METHOD WITH DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION FOR FATIGUE TESTS, in: Proceedings of 38th Danubia-Adria Symposium on Advances in Experimental Mechanics, Greek Society of Experimental Mechanics of Materials, Poros, 2022.
- [66] G. Hollows, N. James, Distortion and Telecentricity, Edmund Optics Knowledge Center (2024). <https://www.edmundoptics.com/knowledge-center/application-notes/imaging/distortion-and-the-telecentricity-specification/> (accessed February 7, 2024).
- [67] B. Pan, H. Xie, Z. Wang, K. Qian, Z. Wang, Study on subset size selection in digital image correlation for speckle patterns, *Opt Express* 16 (2008) 7037. <https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.16.007037>.
- [68] M.A. Sutton, Digital Image Correlation for Shape and Deformation Measurements, in: 2008: pp. 565–600. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-30877-7_20.
- [69] M. Schmid, D. Rath, U. Diebold, Why and How Savitzky–Golay Filters Should Be Replaced, *ACS Measurement Science Au* 2 (2022) 185–196. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmeasuresciau.1c00054>.
- [70] P.S. Palar, K. Zakaria, L.R. Zuhail, K. Shimoyama, R.P. Liem, Gaussian Processes and Support Vector Regression for Uncertainty Quantification in Aerodynamics, in: AIAA Scitech 2021 Forum, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Reston, Virginia, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2021-0181>.
- [71] S.S. Hossain, B.V. Ayodele, S.S. Ali, C.K. Cheng, S.I. Mustapa, Comparative Analysis of Support Vector Machine Regression and Gaussian Process Regression in Modeling Hydrogen Production from Waste Effluent, *Sustainability* 14 (2022) 7245. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14127245>.
- [72] Z. Liu, C. Lyu, J. Huo, S. Wang, J. Chen, Gaussian Process Regression for Transportation System Estimation and Prediction Problems: The Deformation and a Hat Kernel, *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* 23 (2022) 22331–22342. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2022.3155527>.
- [73] M. Kanagawa, P. Hennig, D. Sejdinovic, B.K. Sriperumbudur, Gaussian Processes and Kernel Methods: A Review on Connections and Equivalences, (2018). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1807.02582>.
- [74] C.E. Rasmussen, C.K.I. Williams, Gaussian Processes for Machine Learning, The MIT Press, 2005. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/3206.001.0001>.
- [75] J. Wang, An Intuitive Tutorial to Gaussian Process Regression, *Comput Sci Eng* 25 (2023) 4–11. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCSE.2023.3342149>.

- [76] R.H. Byrd, P. Lu, J. Nocedal, C. Zhu, A Limited Memory Algorithm for Bound Constrained Optimization, *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing* 16 (1995) 1190–1208. <https://doi.org/10.1137/0916069>.
- [77] scikit-learn developers, Gaussian Processes, (2023). https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/gaussian_process.html (accessed January 18, 2024).
- [78] A. Botchkarev, Performance Metrics (Error Measures) in Machine Learning Regression, Forecasting and Prognostics: Properties and Typology, *ArXiv.Org* (2018). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1809.03006>.
- [79] V. Plevris, G. Solorzano, N.P. Bakas, M.E.A. Ben Seghier, Investigation of performance metrics in regression analysis and machine learning-based prediction models, in: *European Community on Computational Methods in Applied Sciences*, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.23967/eccomas.2022.155>.
- [80] N. Moës, J. Dolbow, T. Belytschko, A finite element method for crack growth without remeshing, *Int J Numer Methods Eng* 46 (1999) 131–150. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0207\(19990910\)46:1<131::AID-NME726>3.0.CO;2-J](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0207(19990910)46:1<131::AID-NME726>3.0.CO;2-J).
- [81] I. Sobel, G. Feldman, An Isotropic 3x3 Image Gradient Operator, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.1912.4965>.
- [82] V. Veselý, J. Sobek, L. Šestáková, P. Frantík, S. Seitl, Multi-parameter crack tip stress state description for estimation of fracture process zone extent in silicate composite WST specimens, *Frattura Ed Integrità Strutturale* 7 (2013) 69–78. <https://doi.org/10.3221/IGF-ESIS.25.11>.
- [83] J.-Z. Zhang, X.-P. Zhou, Fracture process zone (FPZ) in quasi-brittle materials: Review and new insights from flawed granite subjected to uniaxial stress, *Eng Fract Mech* 274 (2022) 108795. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2022.108795>.
- [84] C.W. Lim, G. Zhang, J.N. Reddy, A higher-order nonlocal elasticity and strain gradient theory and its applications in wave propagation, *J Mech Phys Solids* 78 (2015) 298–313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmps.2015.02.001>.